

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MALOTHA****FIRST NAME: EUNICE REFILOE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA - 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MS Word Office 365 on Windows 11 Pro)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401

1. Which of the following options is incorrect concerning academic essay writing?

- Using multiple punctuations helps retain the meaning of a sentence.¹**
- Start the process of writing sufficiently early.
- Conduct thorough and relevant research.
- Define and analyze the problem before developing an initial plan.

2. Which of the following is not a correct statement? Plagiarism is:

- wrong.
- ethical.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 19.

² Ibid., 34.

- unfair
 - an academic offense.
3. Which of the following statements depicts a diligent researcher?
- Merely gathers information.
 - Plans last draft first.
 - Utilizes all honest feedback.
 - Methodically interrogates an identified problem to resolve it for the benefit of humanity.³**
4. Research is distinguishable from belief systems because it is:
- non-evidence based.
 - subjective.
 - evidence based.⁴**
 - experience based.
5. Source citation is essential for several reasons. Which of the following is inaccurate?
- Source citation acknowledges the originator of the cited work.
 - Source citation reassures readers that the research is grounded in credible literature.
 - Source citation is not subject matter oriented.⁵**

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

⁴ Ibid., 136.

⁵ Ibid., 141.

- Source citation enables readers to locate the source of the cited material.

6. Which of the following statements is accurate?

- The notes and author-date styles are not the most prevalent citation styles.
- The note-style citation does not require the writer to refer to footnotes or endnotes.
- In the note-style citation, the full citation of sources is done through a bibliography.⁶**
- In the note-style citation, the full citation of sources is done through a reference list.

7. Dissertation research requires a support structure made up of:

- the student only.
- more than just the student.⁷**
- major professor and supervisory committee.
- other research students and researchers from various institutions

8. A dissertation consists of four components arranged in the following order:

- dissertation, prospectus, concept paper, and manuscript.
- concept paper, dissertation, prospectus, and manuscript.
- concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript.⁸**
- concept paper, manuscript, prospectus, dissertation.

⁶ Ibid., 142.

⁷ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

⁸ Ibid., 2.

9. Which statement is inaccurate?

- The Bluebook is the only legal citation system.⁹**
- Legal citation facilitates ease of access to source material.
- A legal citation must be precise.
- Legal citation facilitates future research in the related subject matter.

10. Citation sentences and clauses are instrumental in legal documents. Which of the following statements is accurate?

- Only academic legal documents employ citation sentences and clauses.
- Only non-academic legal documents employ citation sentences and clauses.
- While a citation sentence is punctuated like a regular sentence, a citation clause is like a phrase.¹⁰**
- While a citation sentence is like a phrase, a citation clause is punctuated like a regular sentence.

⁹ Mary M. Prince ed, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, Nineteenth edition (Cambridge: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 1.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 4.

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- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.